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The University Tutorial Action Plan

Experience in the School of Civil Engineering of the Universitat Politècnica de Valencia.

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ABSTRACT

The *Universitat Politècnica de València* (UPV), as part of the INTEGRA program, aims at reducing the impact of first-year students when joining the University life. One of the fundamental pillars of the program is PATU (University Tutorial Action Plan), which together with the Welcome Days eases the integration of new students into the University.

The main aim of this program is to help new students in their integration into the academic and social university life, as well as, to reduce the impact of access to the University, to inform students about relevant aspects of their studies, to increase student participation in the university life, and to advise students in a group and/or individual way about academic aspects or other, to help them to configure their formative itinerary and to optimize their academic performance.

This paper presents the organization, results and experiences of faculty-tutors of the Civil Engineering School at UPV, as well as the evaluation of the benefits obtained by the students of the Bachelor's Degree in Civil Engineering participating in the program.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Education Research, Engineering Skills, Attractiveness of Engineering Education

Keywords: mentoring, first-year student, Civil Engineering degree, faculty-tutor

INTRODUCTION

The *Universitat Politècnica de València* (UPV) launched some years ago a mentoring programme for first-year students known as PATU (The University Tutorial Action Plan) [1], [2]. The main objective of this programme is to make easier new students adaptation to the university context. This kind of initiative is common in many universities worldwide and its utility has been proved to smooth the beginning of first year students at the university [3], [4].

The program began to arise in 2000, within the context of the EUROPA Project (*Una Enseñanza Orientada al Aprendizaje*, A Learning-oriented Education) of the Vice-Rectorate for Academic Coordination and Student Affairs. This project integrated five different programmes which aimed at adapting to changes in university education

and to promote and improve the learning-teaching process between students and teachers. One of the programmes was the *Ayuda al Mejoramiento del Aprendizaje* learning, providing alternative tools and teaching methods to ease self-learning [5]. The sub-programme AMA3 was devoted to faculty-tutors and its objective was to promote students orientation through their studies. Indeed, it was recognized the convenience for new students to have a leading figure representing the institution to help them with studying techniques and to look after them from a personal and academic perspectives.

In 2004, the new Vice-Rectorate for Students Affairs and Campus Life launched the INTEGRA program, which main objective is to help students to integrate into

academic and social university life [6]. The program is composed of three actions: Welcome Days (*Jornadas de Acogida*), different levelling courses and the PATU. The Civil Engineering School (ETSICCP for the Spanish acronym of *Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros de Caminos, Canales y Puertos*) of UPV develops the INTEGRA programme for more than 10 years. The present paper presents how the PATU programme has been organized for the last editions, as well as presenting the results of a survey and questionnaire responded by new students who have participated in the programme during the 2016-17 academic year.

1 THE UPV TUTORIAL ACTION PLAN AT THE CIVIL ENGINEERING

1.1 Organization

All new students at ETSICCP receive information about the Welcome Days that take place in September (Fig. 1), just before the beginning of classes. Eventhough participating in the programme is elective, each new student is assigned to a faculty-tutor and to a student-tutor who will mentor him during the first academic year.

Fig. 1. Brochure of Welcome Days at ETSICCP-UPV.

During the 2016-17 academic year, each faculty-tutor had a student-tutor and, initially, a group composed of 15 first year students. This data varies from one year to another depending on the registration numbers and on teachers and students finally enrolled as mentors. The general organization of the programme is outlined in figure 2. The INTEGRA faculty member in charge of the programme at ETSICCP is the Vice-dean for Student Affairs.

Fig. 2. General organization of the PATU programme (adapted from [1]).

To stimulate students to enroll, the school assigns 1 ECTS (equivalent to 30 student working hours) to the academic curriculum of new students that participate in the Welcome Days and that follow and complete the PATU programme. The requirements to get this ECTS are: to actively participate in at least 6 meetings (group or individual), to attend formative sessions organized by ICE (Institute for Education Sciences), and finally, to evaluate the programme.

If a new student does not participate in the Welcome Days, the faculty-tutor must contact him to call him to group meetings so that he can join the programme at any time. The Vice-Dean for Student Affairs suggests a minimum meeting calendar; participants might adjust this schedule depending on the circumstances and needs. The proposed calendar for the 2016-17 academic year is presented in table 1.

Table 1. Proposed minimum meetings calendar at ETSICCP.

Session	Day	Hours	Month	Organized by	Place
Session 1: Allocation Planning	September 1 st	11:30 to 12:30h	SEPTEMBER	INTEGRA Responsible	Assembly Hall
Sesión 2: Information ETSICCP/UPV	September 15 th	12:15 to 14:15h	SEPTEMBER	Student-Tutor	Computer class
Session 3: Learning strategies	September 22 nd	12:15 to 14:15h	SEPTEMBER	Tutorial Group	Determined by the group
Sesión 4: Individual Tutoring	October 6 th	12:15 to 14:15h	OCTOBER	Faculty-Tutor	Determined by the group
Session 5: Identify and solve problems	October 27 th	12:15 to 14:15h	OCTOBER	Tutorial Group	Determined by the group
Session 6: Follow-up The End	February 2 nd	12:15 to 14:15h	FEBRUARY	Tutorial Group	Determined by the group

As it can be observed, the main part of the programme takes place during the first term, especially during September. Although the reason for this is the need for tutorial action just at the beginning of their arrival to the university, students generally complain about the high number of meetings at that time.

1.2 Faculty- tutors experience

During the 2016-2017 academic year, faculty-tutors authors of this paper mentored 20 new students and were coordinated with 3 student-tutors. In view of the surveys and the examination results, the balance is positive and the experience modestly contributed to improve the education system at ETSICCP (All but one of the students surveyed passed all subjects of the first semester). It also helped young new students at this new stage of their life.

In our opinion, the faculty-tutor must not be mythicized and the student must not see him as a person with answers for every question and with irrefutable opinions. Nevertheless, teachers that decide to take part of this programme must have some skills, like empathy, resilience, polyvalence, etc.; that, anyway, are likely to appear in teaching professionals [8].

For this reason it is important that the faculty-tutors are people capable of giving their time (little time) to meet students and listen to them, that they are mature enough to show possible solutions to problems that arise, that they show enough understanding and openness for the communication to be smooth and that they know their own limits to be able to indicate where students might find solutions in case of a problem being beyond the tutors reach.

All of this should be done without disrespectful confidence and without losing authority. The aim is to create a pleasant atmosphere where the student can feel comfortable, but the roles and the limits of privacy should be kept all the time.

1.3 Evaluation of the student benefits

To conclude the programme, which lasts one academic year, a survey and a questionnaire were developed. In addition with the students academic results during

the first semester, this survey and questionnaire will let know their opinion and propose improvements for further editions of the PATU programme.

The survey is composed of 20 questions developed with the Likert technique [7] with five answer levels. Questions are grouped in 4 groups of 5 questions, related to the following dimensions: general assessment of the PATU programme, assessment of the relationship with the student-tutor, assessment of the relationship with the faculty-tutor and, finally, aspects to be improved in the future. Table 2 presents the survey.

Table 2. Survey to assess the students opinion on the PATU programme.

		TA	A	Ind	D	TD
1	It was interesting to participate in PATU					
2	I would recommend it to all new students at the UPV					
3	I would recommend it to all new students of the ETSICCP (even if it is not their first year at the UPV)					
4	PATU is only interesting the first year at the UPV					
5	All the information that PATU has provided me, could have been given to me in a talk in a single session					
6	The relationship with our student-tutor has been fluid					
7	It has been interesting to be able to speak with students of higher years					
8	The relationship with our student-tutor has facilitated my integration into the School					
9	The relationship with our student tutor has helped us to better prepare the exams					
10	I do not think there is a need for a student-tutor					
11	The relationship with our faculty-tutor has been fluid					
12	It has been interesting to be able to speak with a teacher of non-academic subjects					
13	The relationship with our faculty-tutor has facilitated my integration into the School					
14	The relationship with our faculty-tutor has served us to have confidence and to feel comfortable in the School					
15	I do not think there is a need for a faculty-tutor					
16	I would like the PATU program to continue in later courses					
17	All the aspects that have been discussed in the meetings seem interesting to me					
18	The PATU program only serves to channel the complaints and problems that arise in the classroom					
19	I would like the frequency of meetings to be greater					
20	If doubts or questions arise in the future, I will contact my faculty-tutor					
Totally Agree (TA); Agree (A); Indifferent (Ind); Disagree (D) and Totally Disagree (TD).						

In addition, the survey was completed with a questionnaire (Fig. 3.) where students may express in a more open way their opinion on the programme. Moreover, their academic results (marks) during the first semester were also asked in an anonymous format, to link them with the programme results.

Next section presents the results obtained with the survey and the questionnaire.

Please answer the following questions on this sheet:

1. Indicate the aspects that you most liked about PATU.
2. Indicate the aspects that you least liked about PATU.
3. Discuss the topics that you would like to see covered in the meetings.
4. Would you like to add something else? (Things that you would or would not include in the program, future needs that you think you might have aspects to be improved by faculty- or student-tutors, etc.).
5. Would you like to be a student-tutor? Why?
6. Indicates the grades obtained in the subjects of the first semester:

Drawing = Economics = Physics = Mathematics = Chemistry =

Fig. 3. Questionnaire to assess the students opinion on the PATU programme.

2 RESULTS

2.1 Results of the survey

Table 3 shows the results of the survey conducted to a 19 students pilot group mentored by 3 different faculty-tutors. This sample was selected amongst the 74 students of the Bachelor's Degree in Civil Engineering participating in the PATU programme.

To quantify the results of the survey, the following scores have been adopted: Totally Agree (TA) = 10; Agree (A) = 7.5; Indifferent (Ind) = 5; Disagree (D) = 3.5; and Totally Disagree (TD) = 0.

The first part of questions dealt with general aspects of the PATU programme. Surprisingly, students agreed more with statement in question 2 (You would recommend the PATU programme to new UPV students) than with the one in question 1 (It was interesting to participate in the PATU program). The reason for this result can be that although the participation in the programme is well valued, there are still aspects to improve which still produce a slight refusal (i.e., the excessive demanding during the two first months, at the beginning of the academic year). Nonetheless, the majority of the students recommend to participate in the programme, so we can conclude that they consider it a positive initiative to ease their integration into the University.

Table 3. Average and Standard Deviation for the survey questions.

Question	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Average	6.34	7.50	5.89	5.68	5.21	7.03	7.76	5.50	5.37	3.45
Standard D	2.01	1.18	1.89	2.40	2.05	2.49	1.15	2.12	1.89	2.54

Question	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20
Average	8.42	7.76	7.16	7.24	2.66	6.76	6.61	4.71	2.61	7.82
Standard D	1.71	1.64	1.79	1.84	3.14	2.12	1.98	1.22	2.13	1.69

The second part of questions focused on the opinion on the student-tutor. The most positive aspect ranked within the survey was the opportunity to meet and discuss with students studying the same Bachelor's Degree in higher years (question 7). It also has to be pointed out the positive vision of the relationship between new students and student-tutors (question 7). We have also to highlight that either in this

part and in the next one, the formulation of questions 10 and 15 in a negative form has determined the kind of response given by the students. This is a point to be improved during the following years. Indeed, after analyzing the responses, the quantification performed for the data analysis is not adequate for this kind of formulation.

The third part, which aimed at knowing the opinion on the faculty-tutor, was the best ranked. Students gave scores over 7 for every question (except for question 15 for the reason explained before). Question 11 (the relationship with our faculty-tutor was fluid) obtained the highest score. The answers in this part show that faculty-tutors training as well as their motivation, make their participation in the programme successful.

Finally, the fourth part of the survey give interesting results regarding the continuity of the programme for upcoming academic years. Indeed, the majority of students would like the programme to continue during the following academic years. Finally, the application of the programme in the ETSICCP let new students to have a reference faculty during their first stepd in the University. Mainly, they will turn to him in the next future if they any doubt or problem arise, as answers to question 20 support.

2.2 Results of the questionnaire

General results of the questionnaire reveal that satisfaction of new students of the Bachelor's Degree in Civil Engineering with the PATU programma is very high. Students appreciate accompanying done by faculty-tutors and student-tutors. They also highly appreciate to have a reference person to ask doubts or questions related to their new studies.

Regarding negative points of the programme, a generalized complaint is the high number of activities during the first weeks of the programme: a high number of meetings, the assistance to the Welcome Days and the training sessions organized by ICE. This initial concentration of activities has to be reconsidered for further editions. Advantages of providing a huge amount of information during these first weeks must be analyzed and reconsidered. Possible alternatives are to extend these informative activities all along the first four-month period, or let the students ask for information when it will be needed.

The mayority of new students who participated in the PATU programme will be trained to participate in the future as student-tutors. Nevertheless, this willingness is not necessarily altruistic, provided they will get from the school credits as a transfer for they participation in the programme. All but one of the students surveyed passed all subjects of the first semester. Nevertheless, we cannot identify a relationship between the academic results and the participation in the programme.

3 CONCLUSIONS

The analysis performed with the survey and the questionnaire hihlighted the following conclusions.

The best appreciated aspect of the PATU programme by new students is the assignation of a faculty-tutor. The majority has a positive opinion on the relationship between the student and the faculty-tutor.

The relationship with the student-tutors is good and new students of the Bachelor's Degree in Civil Engineering are satisfied with the possibility of meet older students. Nevertheless, they are indifferent to statements like "the relationship with my student-

tutor eased my integration into the School” or “the relationship with my student-tutor helped me to prepare my exams”.

Three conclusions should be highlighted, (1) only one student was reluctant to contact with his faculty-tutor in case he will arise doubts or questions in the future, (2) the majority of students would like the programme to continue during next academic years, and (3) all new students who participated in the PATU programme and were surveyed agreed in recommending future new students to also get involved.

Finally, regarding points to be improved, there is a consensus on the high concentration of activities during the first weeks of the year (meetings, Welcome Days and training sessions). An alternative solution may be to spread these activities during more months.

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